

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Practices in determining challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(01), 1245–1255

Publication history: Received on 12 December 2022; revised on 24 January 2023; accepted on 27 January 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.1.0163>

Abstract

Background: Many institutions have reported a reduction in disruptive and violent behavior, chronic school absences, and disciplinary referrals and suspensions. These conflict resolution programs have also given the young increased self-esteem, self-confidence, and self-respect. Adults play an important part in making sure kids exercise their newly found conflict resolution skills. Therefore, it remains vitally important for school personnel to set an example. All of these programs aim to keep both children and adults in line without resulting to violence.

Aim: The aim of this study was to find out how to address concerns of parents to improve school programs and create positive and functional environment that minimizes disruptive behaviors from learners or from parents.

Methods: The study used a descriptive research design. Descriptive design is suitable wherever the subjects vary among themselves and one is interested to know the extent to which different conditions and situations are obtained among these subjects. The method of gathering data is a survey questionnaire which is a product of a thorough reading of related literature and studies. After the construction, the questionnaire was validated by the experts and was piloted to respondents.

Conclusion: The top 10 answers from the teachers shows positive and good result since it has an overall mean of 3.69 and SD of 0.31 interpreted as very true of me meaning the good result of this study is beyond no doubt. Using the Analysis of Variance, with its level of significance of .05 and its tabular value of 2.68 3 revealed that the computed value of 8.012 is greater than the tabular value, so then the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Same with the p-value of 0.04 since it is less than the level of significant of 0.05 it means that there is a significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents.

Keywords: Attitudes; Behaviors; Challenges; Practices; Parents

1. Introduction

(This part presents in an APA format and IMRaD style of writing which includes the reason why the study is undertaken, purpose of the research and the research questions together with the tested hypothesis/es)

Human nature being what it is, teachers occasionally find themselves working with families whose attitudes are difficult to deal with no matter how positive the teacher's attempts have been. Stress or personally may cause some parents to display responses that range from belligerence to indifference and either extreme is quite daunting to work with. In addition, any classroom teacher can tell that particular situations with parents arise regularly enough to become sources of chronic irritation. Such encounters may be so discouraging or threatening that teachers retreat from future efforts to work with families. But when this happens, children's well-being will suffer, so it is important that teachers that

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teachers develop skills and strategies to help counter the negatives. The establishment of family–school partnerships is a research-supported movement with numerous benefits for students. Family–school partnerships are associated with superior grade point averages, standardized test scores, attendance, home and school behavior, social skills, and adaptation to school (Henderson & Mapp, 2019). They also improve school programs, school climate, family services and support, parent skills and advocacy efforts, family– school–community connections, and support the work of teachers (Epstein, 2019). Despite the many benefits of family–school partnerships, achieving these collaborative relationships remains challenging. Schools want parents to support their practices and teaching efforts, and parents want schools to be responsive to the unique needs of their family and child, but far too often, neither parents nor educators are collaboratively finding ways to maximize the educational experience and academic outcomes of students (Auerbach, 2019; Christenson, 2019; Wanat, 2019). More specifically, discrepant perspectives of a child or the child’s needs have been identified as a factor that initiates and escalates conflict between parents and teachers (Lake & Billingsley, 2019) and negatively impacts parental involvement in school programs (Patel & Stevens, 2019). Both parents and teachers may want what is best for a student, but their expectations and perceptions of a particular child can vary. This leaves educators and parents struggling to develop and foster family–school partnerships in a conflict-laden climate with limited knowledge about how best to handle these conflicts (Lake & Billingsley, 2019). Many barriers exist that challenge the formation of family–school partnerships. Christenson (2019) categorizes these barriers as those affecting families, educators, and those directly related to the family–school relationship. For example, family barriers that interfere with positive partnerships include: assuming a passive role in the educational process, distrust of educators, and educator unresponsiveness to family needs and wishes. Educator barriers include: fear of conflict with parents, concerns about families’ abilities to assist with school-related issues, negative communication with families regarding a child’s academic progress, and difficulty seeing parents as partners in the educational process. Finally, barriers related to the family–school relationship include: communication that occurs strictly when problems arise, lack of information and resources about how collaboration between families and schools should occur, lack of perspective-taking from both parties, failure to accept a partnership orientation, a win–lose attitude when presented with a conflict, and varying perceptions of a child’s performance (Christenson, 2019). Effective family–school partnerships are challenging in the best of circumstances. But when parents and teachers disagree about educational decisions related to a child, these relationships are further complicated. Lake and Billingsley (2019) examined factors contributing to parent–school conflict in special education and identified the following eight factors: discrepant views of a child or child’s needs, trust, communication, constraints, reciprocal power, valuation, service delivery, and knowledge. Their study did not directly investigate the impact of discrepant views on students; however, it provided evidence that the discrepant views “resulted in an unwillingness to take the risks necessary to continue communicating about the needs of the child” (Lake & Billingsley, 2019, p. 249).

Behavior problems in a classroom increase the stress levels for both the teacher and pupils, disrupt the flow of lessons and conflict with both learning objectives and the processes of learning. They also change the classroom dynamic as the focus of attention shifts from the academic tasks at hand to the distractions provided by disruptive behaviors. Typically, one or two pupils are identifiable as ‘problems’, sometimes they act in ways that compound management difficulties by inciting each other and, possibly, others in the class into disruptive activities. The usual response to problematic behavior is to identify the child(ren) involved as ‘the problem’, to focus on them as a source of ‘trouble’ and to devise strategies specifically to deal with their inappropriate behavior. However, a classroom is an environment with its own ecology, including teacher, pupils and their interrelationships, the equipment, books and a range of activities which all interact to influence the behavior of the room’s inhabitants. To complicate things further, both teacher and pupils bring into class experiences and issues from the wider ecological systems in which they live and function e.g., the rest of the school community, home, family/whanau, community and the wider world. Simply targeting interventions at individual children in the classroom may not actually solve a classroom behavior problem. Indeed, focusing on individuals may lead one to ignore examination of systemic problems in teacher–pupil relations, the management and teaching styles of the teacher, the curriculum and the skills required by students to access it, the order in which activities are scheduled, and a whole host of other aspects of the classroom and wider school ecology. It also has to be remembered that children bring to school all sorts of concerns, distresses, reactions and patterns of behavior established, permitted and supported outside of the classroom itself. Thus, targeting a child as ‘the problem’ may divert one’s attention from a careful examination of the classroom ecology or that of the wider school and the family and community environments within which the school is embedded. Equally, children learn to discriminate the behaviors required in a variety of settings and thus can learn to behave differently if appropriate and desired behaviors are signaled, encouraged and supported in any given setting: it also needs to be assessed against the background of the environment in which it occurs. To place problem behavior in context, 88 percent of a sample of 42 New Zealand teachers responding to a questionnaire rated classroom mismanagement as ‘sometimes’ or ‘very often’ a cause of problematic classroom behavior (Johansen, Little & Akin-Little, 2019). Of concern was the fact that many of these teachers had had minimal preservice training in behavior management and in service professional development was considered by some to be of little benefit or not

commonly offered. The classroom management strategies employed by teachers in the classroom can also affect how they deal with eventual parents' concerns and complaints later on.

In the study by Johansen, Little and Akin-Little (2019) cited above accurately represents teacher awareness that poor classroom management is an important factor associated with disruptive behavior, then it would follow that interventions which target teaching skills and classroom behavior management have the potential to produce significant impacts on disruptive behavior. According to the Elton Report (2016, cited in the Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills 2019, section 65, p.15), it was estimated that in the United Kingdom 80 percent of disruptive behavior was attributable "to poor classroom organization, planning and teaching". According to the report, British teachers stated behaviors such as talking out-of-turn, and other forms of persistent low-level disruption as the most frequent and stress-inducing because of their constantly disruptive effect on both classroom activities and the teaching-learning process. Important factors identified related to teacher confidence and competence, their ability to engage children in the curriculum and for teachers to have good group management skills so that the class focus was on appropriate behavior. Effective teaching and positively functioning classrooms with low levels of disruptive behavior require planning and consistency. Factors which have been found to contribute to these outcomes identified in a literature review by Kern and Clemens (2017) are

- Clear, simple rules and expectations which are consistently and fairly applied.
- Predictability of events and activities through establishing routines, information, cues and signals about forthcoming transitions and changes, as well as for content, duration, and consequences for activities.
- Frequent use of praise, both verbal and non-verbal. Teacher praise has demonstrated effects on both those earning it and those nearby. Verbal praise should be specific and descriptive. Teachers should try to provide a child with at least four praise statements for every reprimand.
- Because disruptive behavior is often associated with learning deficits, task difficulty needs to be monitored. All students need to have the required entry skills and ability to successfully engage in assigned activities. Participation and learning can only follow successful access to the curriculum and encouragement to sustain activity.
- Opportunities to respond and participate in the classroom activities, to use the materials and to respond to requests must be inclusive of all children in the class. Strategies to increase the engagement of all students include having everyone write answers to some teacher questions rather than just seeking one correct response.
- Seating arrangements: For older students (10 years and above) seating in rows works better than group seating.
- Effective instructions and commands need to be preceded by getting the pupils' attention, and then presented clearly one at a time as "do's", in a firm (not angry) voice, with time to comply and praise for compliance. Precise, specific, direct and paced (one-at-a-time) instructions delivered in a calm and quiet voice, followed by praise for compliance have been found most effective.
- Sequencing of activities, so that easy and brief tasks are interspersed with longer and more demanding ones, enhances engagement and learning as well as reducing disruption. Preceding difficult activities with a few simple ones has been found to enhance transition to a new activity as has scheduling active learning after breaks before moving on to more passive activities so that children have time to adapt to quieter routines.
- Pace of instruction is best if it is brisk. This can be achieved by increasing the rate of instruction or decreasing the pauses between student response and the presentation of the next task. Increased pace needs to be managed so that students do not lose opportunities to respond and access reinforcement.
- Choice and access to preferred activities increases engagement and reduces problem behavior. Using children's own special interests as the basis for activities can significantly increase engagement. While these elements may each present as common knowledge to teachers, the consistent and skilled application of them as a systematically used package of effective teaching strategies is what increases the probability of enhanced learning and reduced problematic behavior. To assist teachers with particular management problems it is sometimes necessary to implement specific interventions.

Effective communication is essential to create strong school-home partnerships and to increase parental involvement. Just as teachers are skilled in the art of teaching, they also require knowledge and skills to effectively communicate with their parent community. A number of communication opportunities are currently available to teachers, ranging from school-to-home communication books to parent conferences to the use of internet technology. Importantly, teachers should note that communication is rarely a discrete, individual act but rather occurs within the context of ongoing exchanges (Adler & Rodman, 2017). Every communication exchange, regardless of format, should reflect a thoughtful, planned approach and should be viewed as an opportunity for teachers to promote parent partnerships and, ultimately, to support student learning.

Huang and Mason found that while parent involvement appears beneficial to some parents and children, other research indicates that African Americans are uninvolved in urban school setting. However, in their semi-structured group interviews, Huang and Mason found from their data analysis that African Americans are motivated to be involved in their children's learning, "when they can form relationships (with other adults), when they know they can influence their children's learning, and when they can find ways for their children to achieve success." All of the participants in their research were involved in the family literacy program, which indicates that those who were interviewed prefer the community environment that they don't find at school-based activities. Many literacy programs facilitate meeting with families and community, which eventually may motivate parents to be involved in school activities. However, Daniel-White argues that parent involvement programs "have been developed in schools in ways that are valued by middle class parents to the exclusion of language minority families, their language, and their culture" (3). She also claims that many programs are founded upon an ideology that minority families have less ability in parenting or "a cultural deficit approach to parenting." Finally, Danielle-White claims that school-based programs do not provide immigrant parents the tools they need to help their children. The research demonstrates that many parents are ready to be involved. They believe that children's schooling is a normal responsibility regardless of quantity, interest, or concerns about children's ability. They are willing to be involved because they believe it will make a difference in the child's life. Those who feel confident believe that their help will cause positive student outcomes. Lastly, parents decide to be involved in homework because they sense an invitation from their child or the child's teacher. Thus, the parents believe their help for the student is wanted or expected. Walker et al. insists that parent involvement is a powerful tool for letting parents and family know what the child is learning, gives parents and children a reason to talk about school, and gives teachers an opportunity to hear from parents about their children.

TNS Social research (September 2003-June 2004) stated that parents' attitudes towards education were generally very positive. The majority (97%) agreed that a good education would help their child to get ahead in life. While 93% thought the qualifications were important to their child's future, 90% also agreed that children learn important life skills at school. Three quarters of parents (76%) agreed that their child's school is good at communicating with them and the majority (86%) agreed that their child's teachers do a great job. Just over a fifth (22%) felt that their child's school tended to be too interested in bright children at the expense of the others, although only 7% thought that the school takes too much interest in their child's home life. Just under a fifth of parents/guardians (18%) thought that most of the things their child learns at school are not relevant to real life. A small proportion (14%) of parents saw it as acceptable that if their child did not want to study now, s/he could study when s/he was older. Their study was based on to identify whether there were any differences in parents' attitudes towards attendance between the general population and a group of parents whose children were currently not attending school. This research has not identified any differences in the attitudes of parents in the general population. Research indicates that most parents show considerable interest in their child's school, and this is equally the case for parents of children who have attendance problems. In an Ofsted report (2019) on attendance and behavior in secondary schools, it has been found (O'Keefe, 2017) that most schools usually enjoyed good working relationships with parents. In fact, most of the parents/guardians said they wanted more contact with schools. The majority of parents were appreciative of the concern and time given by head teachers and staff, even when approached about issues concerning their children's attendance or behavior. However, it was also found that a small proportion of parents/guardians were very uncooperative with the schools, and their attitudes, whether confrontational or passive, served to reinforce their children's negative attitude towards school. In a study of attitude to school attendance in seven Local Education Authorities (LEAs) in England, it was found that most parents/guardians believed that children who did not attend school regularly would under- perform in school work, and that it was necessary for young people to get qualifications. However, the findings also indicated that parents/guardians of children who truant tended to hold different attitudes from parents of children who do not have problems with attendance. Fewer parents/guardians of children with school attendance problems believed that pupils who did not attend regularly would do badly in their schoolwork, and similarly, a smaller proportion of these parents/guardians believed that young people needed qualifications. This group was also less likely to think that their children's safety was at risk if they were not at school, and were less likely to believe that regular school attendance was important. There were also statistically significant differences between the views of both sets of parents with regard to when children should miss school, with a significantly higher proportion of parents of children with attendance problems agreeing that children should miss school to see the doctor, the dentist, or to help out at home.

Research illustrating the importance of parent involvement for the school success of adolescents spans nearly two decades. Duncan (1969), for example, compared the attendance, achievement, and drop-out rate of two junior high classes. In one class, students' parents had individual meetings with counsellors before their children entered junior high school. In the other class, students' parents did not meet with counsellors. After three years, students whose parents had met individually with the school counsellors had significantly higher attendance, better grade point averages, and lower drop-out rates.

Lucas, Henze, and Donato (2017) also found that schools play a central role in determining levels of parent involvement in students' learning. In a study of six high schools in California and Arizona that were providing an environment in which language minority students and others achieve academic success, the authors found that the schools actively encouraged parent involvement. Through newsletters, parent advisory committees, parent nights, and student parent-teacher conferences, the high schools fostered families' active participation in their teens' education. Dornbusch and Ritter (2016) studied the effects of parent involvement in high school activities on student outcomes. The study was based on questionnaire data from students, parents, and teachers at six San Francisco Bay Area high schools. The authors found that regardless of educational background, adolescents whose parents attended school functions received higher grades than adolescents whose parents did not. The authors also found that the lowest levels of family involvement in school programs and processes were among the parents of average students, minority students, students in step-families, and students in single-parent households. It was concluded that without interventions designed to encourage greater family involvement in these subgroups, educational and economic inequalities will persist for many poor, minority students. Researchers must also consider race as an actor when studying parental involvement in education. Hill et al. (2019) indicate that the race of the parent(s) impacts parental involvement in education. In particular, African Americans have stronger parental involvement than European Americans (Hill et al., 2019). However, some research has found the opposite to be true (c.f. Seyfried & Chung, 2019). Others, like Hill and Tyson (2019), state that it is unclear whether or not parental involvement varies across race/ethnicity. This proposed study aims to clarify this. A study conducted by (George, 2018). Search Institute found that four practices of parental involvement discussions about homework, discussions about school and school work, helping with homework, and attending school meetings and events decline significantly between grades six and twelve. The study revealed that by the junior or senior year in high school relatively few adolescents have parents who maintain an active interest in their education. It has been emphasized that (National Research Council [NRC], 2001; U.S. Department of Education, 2000) the family involvement is the strongest predictor of child outcomes. This dimension associated significantly with children's motivation to learn, kept attention, task persistence, receptive vocabulary skills, and low conduct problems. Family involvement in education has been identified as a beneficial factor in young children's learning.

This study is guided by conflict resolution theory. Conflict resolution theory guides the informal or formal process that two or more parties use to find a peaceful solution to their dispute.

A number of common cognitive and emotional traps, many of them unconscious, can exacerbate conflict and contribute to the need to engage conflict resolution theory to come to an agreement. Both parties to a conflict typically think they're right (and the other side is wrong) because they quite literally can't get out of our own heads. Educators have identified four conflict resolution strategies that can be used in a variety of school-based settings. These four conflict resolution strategies include peer mediation, process curriculum, peaceable classrooms, and peaceable schools. All four approaches provide youth with the necessary tools to help cope with conflict. Educators can work with their local school district to determine which approach to use for the best results. Many experts assert that the youth will learn to recognize and resolve problems before they escalate. Many schools and communities have adopted the peer mediation approach to teaching conflict resolution. Under this approach, trained mediators work with their peers to resolve conflict. Mediation programs aim to reduce traditional use of punishment, such as suspension, detention, and expulsion. Peer mediation programs have proven effective in most cases involving conflict turned violent. As a result, these programs have become highly valued among teachers.

Teachers also have the option of devoting a separate course, or curriculum, to the principles and processes of conflict resolution. The process curriculum approach aims to teach kids how to solve disputes by helping them envision scenarios that could occur in the future. This approach introduces ways to solve problems before they arise. The same applies for the peaceable classroom approach, except that it integrates conflict resolution into the daily curriculum and overall management of the classroom. The peaceable classroom approach reinforces cooperative behavior and encourages the acceptance of diversity. It also teaches caring and effective communication.

Schools that have adopted the peaceable classroom approach typically have the entire school involved the process. In fact, many schools have adopted the peaceable school approach, which incorporates the above three approaches. A peaceable school creates an environment where everyone works together toward conflict resolution, including students, teachers, and administrators. The peaceable school approach ensures that the entire school remains watchful of possible conflicts.

The aforementioned conflict resolution programs have helped schools, communities, and juvenile justice settings improve their overall climate. Many institutions have reported a reduction in disruptive and violent behavior, chronic school absences, and disciplinary referrals and suspensions. These conflict resolution programs have also given the young increased self-esteem, self-confidence, and self-respect. Adults play an important part in making sure kids

exercise their newly found conflict resolution skills. Therefore, it remains vitally important for school personnel to set an example. All of these programs aim to keep both children and adults in line without resulting to violence (Conflict Resolution at School & on the Playground, n.d.).

Therefore, this study would like to find out how to address concerns of parents. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions: (1.) What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment and length of service? (2.) What is the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different practices or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents? (3.) Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different practices or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents when they are grouped accordingly? and (4.) Based from the results of the study, what practices in resolving challenging behaviors and attitude of parents can be proposed?

Furthermore, this study hypothesized that there is no significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents when they are grouped accordingly. The techniques in dealing with challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents were described based on the assessment of the respondents. The data were gathered through a survey, unstructured interview and documentary analysis. Then, the data were treated statistically using percentage, weighted mean and ANOVA. The findings of the aforementioned study were helpful in proposing techniques in resolving challenging behaviors and attitude of parents

In view thereof, the above theory and concepts served as basis for the researchers to conduct this study. The reviewed literature and studies are all very viable and they helped the researcher conceptualized the study and established the relationship of variables. Figure 1 explains further the relationship of the different variables discussed in the study.

Figure 1 Relationship of variables in the study

As shown in the figure, the researcher first determined the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, educational attainment and length of service.

Then, the researcher determined the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents.

This was the basis in proposing strategy of working to resolve challenging behaviors and attitudes of parents.

The researcher believes that this study is beneficial to the following:

Students will benefit from this study considering that parent’s involvement has a positive relation with general children’s performance. This study is relevant to teachers in enhancing parent’s sense of belongingness to school, improving communication between school and parents, and improving positive bonding. Through the results of this

study, principals may determine appropriate process in addressing concerns and complaints initiated by the parents. DepEd officials may develop policy to address parental concerns in collaboration with school community. Furthermore, findings of the study will provide guide to the future researchers and serve as reference to any study similar to what is being investigated by the study at hand.

Meanwhile, for better understanding, the researcher has provided both the conceptual and operational definition of the following terms:

Attitude. This is "a relatively enduring organization of beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards socially significant objects, groups, events or symbols" (Hogg & Vaughan 2019, p. 150). Attitude is the feeling or mental disposition of an individual which influences the human behavior. Attitude is a vital ingredient for the success or failure of children in their optimum development. In this study, this refers to the attitudes of parents in conflict with the responsibilities of the teachers.

Challenging Behaviors. In this study, these can be behaviors of parents where the reasons behind the behavior are difficult to understand or that teachers find hard to accept.

Partnership. This means positive and respectful relationship between teachers and parents.

Resolve. This means finding solutions to the conflicts that may arise between parents and teachers.

2. Material and methods

The researcher used descriptive research design. Descriptive design is suitable wherever the subjects vary among themselves and one is interested to know the extent to which different conditions and situations are obtained among these subjects. The word survey signifies the gathering of data regarding the present conditions. A survey is useful in: (1) providing the value of facts; and (2) focusing attention on the most important things to be reported. In this study, it was used to describe the kinds of thinking of the respondents. Specifically, the type of descriptive aside from the generic descriptive design is status which is problem solving and seeks to answer questions to real facts relating to existing conditions. This is a technique of quantitative description which determines the prevailing conditions in a group of cases chosen for the study. In this study, it was used to describe the non-coercive teaching strategies in a virtual classroom. The method of gathering data is a survey questionnaire which is a product of a thorough reading of related literature and studies. After the construction, the questionnaire was validated by the experts and was piloted to respondents who were not included in the survey and the researcher's colleagues and she asked the help of her former professors in the graduate school in the revision of the survey. The locale of the study was Aniban Central School located at Aniban II, Bacoor City Cavite. At present, the school has 80 teachers. The locale was chosen because the researcher observed the need to create positive and functional environment that minimizes disruptive behaviors from learners or from parents. The respondents were the 80 teachers who were selected using the total enumeration. After the gathering of data and asking permission from the different offices, the gathered data were subjected to statistical treatment of data.

3. Results and discussion

Table 1 Frequency and Percentage of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Age

Age range	Frequency	Percentage
26 - 30	21	26.25%
31 - 35	11	13.75%
36 - 40	19	23.75%
41 - 45	6	7.50%
More than 45	23	28.75%
Overall	80	100%

This chapter comprised the data gathered through the use of survey questionnaires that were systematically presented, analyzed and interpreted following the sequence of the research questions as enumerated and explained in the first chapter.

The table shows the age of the respondents. out of 80 there are 23 respondents or 28.75% within the range of more than 45, the highest frequency while the lowest are in the range of 41 to 45 or 7.50%. most of them are in the middle of age.

Table 2 Frequency and Percentage of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Sex

Student Respondents		
	Frequency	Percentage
Male	12	15.00%
Female	68	85.00%
Overall	80	100%

In terms of sex. There are 12 males and 68 females. The number of females is much greater than male as expected because they are the dominant number in the population.

Table 3 Frequency and Percentage of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

	Frequency	Percentage
Bachelor's degree	46	57.50%
With master's units	27	33.75%
Master's Degree	7	8.75%
Overall	80	100%

In the table 3, 46 teacher-respondents has Bachelor's degree, 27 of the teacher-respondents have their master's units. While 7 of them finish masters' degree.

Table 4 Frequency and Percentage of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of Length of service

	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5 years	11	13.75%
5-10	19	23.75%
11-15	16	20.00%
16-20	16	20.00%
21-25	15	18.75%
More than 25	3	3.75%
Total	80	100%

When it comes to the length of service, 11 have below 5 years of experience in public school as teacher, 19 of them are within the range 5 - 10 years, 16 of them within the range of 11 - 15, 16 of them within the range of 16 - 20, 15 of them within the range of 21 - 25 and 3 of them more than 25 years in service. It indicates that most of the teachers are younger in the service.

3.1. What is the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitude of parents?

Table 5 Weighted Mean of the assessment of the teacher-respondents

	In dealing with parents with challenging behaviors and attitude, I ...	Weighted mean	SD	Interpretation
1.	Take a deep breath and try to remain calm and be rational when parents are rude and demanding.	3.73	0.27	Very true of me
2.	Try to set a positive tone and model an appropriate response, even if it means you must take a few moments to compose yourself.	3.62	0.38	Very true of me
3.	Make sure parents understand that it's their misbehavior I dislike, not them and nothing personal.	3.54	0.46	Very true of me
4.	Give the misbehaving parents a chance to respond positively	3.81	0.19	Very true of me
5.	Never resort to blame or ridicule.	3.79	0.21	Very true of me
6.	Avoid win-lose conflicts or problem-solving.	3.56	0.44	Very true of me
7.	Try to remain courteous in the face of hostility or anger.	3.63	0.37	Very true of me
8.	Treat parents respectfully and politely and be consistent.	3.72	0.28	Very true of me
9.	Try to be an attentive listener.	3.84	0.16	Very true of me
10.	Model the behavior I expect from the parents.	3.49	0.51	Very true of me
11.	Become more aware of cultural differences between me and the arents and among the parents.	3.52	0.48	Very true of me
12.	Avoid labeling students as "always complaining" or "cooperative", "good or bad".	3.63	0.37	Very true of me
13.	Try to understand where the behavior is coming from.	3.75	0.25	Very true of me
14.	Help myself manage negative feelings by reflecting on a past situation in my life where a similar conflict occurred.	3.77	0.33	Very true of me
15.	Share what I feel with our principal or colleague and get suggestions from their best practices.	3.88	0.12	Very true of me
16.	Showing appreciation for their cooperation, feedback and suggestions.	3.73	0.23	Very true of me
17.	Assist them in checking the homework of their children to make them feel that we are partners.	3.69	0.31	Very true of me
18.	Reiterate the importance of attending school academic programs and acknowledge their presence.	3.74	0.26	Very true of me
19.	Work with them in advising their children on study habits	3.66	0.34	Very true of me
20.	Set schedule in discussing academic progress of their children.	3.72	0.28	Very true of me
21.	Encourage the parents to share with me their concerns about their children.	3.74	0.26	Very true of me
22.	Emphasize the strengths and goodness of their children.	3.72	0.28	Very true of me
23.	Do not surprise them with issues and concerns relative to their children.	3.58	0.42	Very true of me
24.	Look for areas where we agree on and I don't force or insist my point especially when the parents are not ready.	3.59	0.41	Very true of me
25.	Inform my principal when I know that things will not be resolved as I planned.	3.82	0.18	Very true of me
	Overall	3.69	0.31	Very true of me

Legend: 3.1 – 4.0 – Always/Very True of Me; 2.1 – 3.0 – Often/True of Me; 1.1 – 2.0 – Sometimes/Moderately True of Me; 0.1 – 1.0 – Never/Not True of Me

These are the result of the assessment of the teacher-respondents on Whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitude of parents. The indicators with the greatest number of positive respond base on the table are the following; 1. Give the misbehaving parents a chance to respond positively. 2. Never resort to blame or ridicule, 3. Treat parents respectfully and politely and be consistent, 4. Treat parents respectfully and politely and be consistent. 5. Treat parents respectfully and politely and be consistent. 6. Help myself manage negative feelings by reflecting on a past situation in my life where a similar conflict occurred. 7. Share what I feel with our principal or colleague and get suggestions from their best practices., 8. Reiterate the importance of attending school academic programs and acknowledge their presence.9. Encourage the parents to share with me their concerns about their children.10. Inform my principal when I know that things will not be resolved as I planned. These are the top ten answers from the teachers' respondents, and it shows positive and good result since it has an overall mean of 3.69 and SD of 0.31 interpreted as very true of me meaning the good result of this study is beyond no doubt.

3.2. Is there a significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attitude of parents when they are grouped accordingly?

Table 6 Teacher-Respondents Techniques when grouped

	P-value	Level of significant (Two Tailed)	ANOVA computed value	ANOVA tabular Value	Decision	Interpretation
Assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not	0.0004	0.05	8.012	2.683	Reject the null	significant

Using the Analysis of Variance, with its level of significance of .05 and its tabular value of 2.68 3 revealed that the computed value of 8.012 is greater than the tabular value, so then the decision is to reject the null hypothesis. Same with the p-value of 0.04 since it is less than the level of significant of 0.05 it means that there is a significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attituded of parents.

3.3. Based on the results of the study, what techniques in resolving challenging behaviors and attitude of parents can be proposed?

The researcher wanted to propose the top ten survey answered by the respondents since it is proven techniques and already apply in a real-life situation in resolving challenging behaviors and attitude of parents.

4. Conclusion

In view of the aforementioned findings, the researcher has drawn the following conclusions:

- The top ten answers from the teachers' respondents shows positive and good result since it has an overall mean of 3.69 and SD of 0.31 interpreted as very true of me meaning the good result of this study is beyond no doubt.
- The p-value of 0.04 since it is less than the level of significant of 0.05 it means that there is a significant difference in the assessment of the teacher-respondents on whether they use the different techniques or not, in dealing with the challenging behaviors and attituded of parents.
- The researcher wanted to propose the top ten survey answered by the respondents since it is proven techniques and already apply in a real-life situation in resolving challenging behaviors and attitude of parents.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

I cannot express enough thanks for their support and encouragement: Dr. Dennis G. Caballes my professor, Dr. Editha M. Attendido our City Schools Division Superintendent and Mrs. Nancy M. Eclarinal our school principal.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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